

European guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System for zoonotic diseases: a needs assessment using implementation theory

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INTRODUCTION

Zoonotic diseases (zoonoses) are caused by infections shared between animals and humans¹.

To deal with zoonoses, European countries need to organise prevention, signaling and control by stimulating One Health (OH) collaboration. OH collaboration is referred to as collaboration between different disciplines and sectors.

This will be referred to as: **One Health Risk Analysis System (OHRAS)**

GUIDELINES can be supportive to strengthen One Health collaboration. A global guideline exists², but is not tailored to specific needs of **EUROPE**.

AIM

- To understand what the perceived needs and requirements are to build an OHRAS. The results will be used for the guidelines.

METHODS

- 3 Focus Group Discussions.
- 9 Semi Structured Interviews.
- Transdisciplinary Research.
- Participants from 9 different European countries.
- 19 professionals from the public, veterinarian and food institutions.
- 5 senior policy makers from ministries of health, agriculture and environment.

Conceptual framework:

In this study we used an adaptive Active Implementation Framework³.

RESULTS

This study showed that there are certain needs and requirements to build an OHRAS and practical requirements for the guidelines. In addition, participants expressed the importance of certain values and principles in the context of OHRAS.

1 Needs and requirements to build an OHRAS

2 Key principles for One Health collaboration in the context of OHRAS

RESPONSIBILITY
TRUST **COMMUNICATION**
RESPECT **BUILD IN PEACE TIME**
SHARED GOALS

3 Practical requirements for the guidelines

CONCLUSIONS

European implementation guidelines:

- are necessary.
- need to be developed by and for professionals working in the area of zoonoses.
- should focus on implementation and operation.
- should focus on how to nurture key values and principles that are essential for collaboration in the context of OHRAS.

This study added to the knowledge gaps that:

- underlying values such as responsibility, trust and respect can drive behaviour, decision-making, collaboration and governance processes in relation to building an OHRAS.

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